

PECULIARITIES OF FUNCTIONING OF TEXT CATEGORIES IN A FILM TEXT

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Abstract

The presence in linguistics of various approaches to the study of text and discourse allows one to interpret the text as a product of thought-speech activity, as a speech realization of the author's idea and a communicative unit of the highest level, realized in both written and oral speech. Due to the need to take into account the extralingual component in the process of generating and perceiving the text, the concept of discourse is used, which is traditionally understood as a coherent text combined with extralingual factors, a text taken in the event aspect.

Keywords: film text, film discourse, polymodality, polycode.

Stating the problem. In linguistics, the complex language of cinematography is considered as a special type of text / discourse. In scientific literature, the relative terms "film discourse", "film text", "film narrative", "film dialogue" are used. According to Y. M. Lotman's views, films are texts along with poems and symphonies [7, p. 14]. Y. G. Tsyvian defines the film text "as a discrete sequence of continuous sections of the text ..., a chain of nuclear frames" [12, p. 109]. In modern linguistic studies, the terms "film text" and "film discourse" are not sufficiently clearly distinguished. In this article, it will be considered what is common between these concepts and what is decisive in their differentiation, in order to more clearly visualize the structure of these concepts and determine which linguistic combination is more productive and relevant for modern linguistics.

Recent theoretical research analyses. Based on the understanding of discourse as the realization of the text and taking into account the fact that many researchers (Y. M. Lotman (1992), Y. G. Tsyvian (1984), Y. M. Usov (1980), A. V. Fedorov (2000), K. B. Ivanova (2000), etc.) wrote about the work of cinematography as a text, we will dwell on the most common definitions of the term "film text".

Y. G. Tsyvian writes: "In a certain approximation, any film can be defined as a discrete sequence of continuous sections of text. We will call this sequence a film text" [12].

Numerous definitions reveal only certain characteristics of the film text, without reflecting it as a communicative whole. "The message recorded on the film received the name film text in the scientific literature" [3] "Film text – a message containing information and presented in any form and genre of cinematography (play, documentary, animation, educational, science fiction film)" [2, p. 36]. The above definitions indicate the communicative nature and genre diversity of the film text, but do not reveal its essence.

According to Y. M. Usov's definition, the film text is a dynamic system of audio-visual images, or "a dynamic system of plastic forms that exists in the screen conditions of space-time dimensions and transmits the sequence of development of the artist's thoughts about the world and about himself through audio-visual

means" [11, p. 17]. This definition takes into account such important factors as the special space-temporal mode of existence of the film text – "screenness", and the audio-visual way of its perception. At the same time, its communicative orientation is not taken into account.

The most comprehensive definition of film text can be found in the monograph of H. G. Slyshkin and M. O. Yefremova "Film text (experience of linguistic and cultural analysis)": "a clear, full and complete message expressed with the help of verbal (linguistic) and non-verbal (iconic) signs, organized according to the idea of a collective functionally differentiated author with the help of cinematographic codes, fixed on a material carrier and intended for reproduction on the screen and audio-visual perception by the audience ... The film text itself is created with the help of cinematographic codes, which include perspective, frame, light, plan, plot, artistic space, montage. Each of the mentioned cinematographic codes can become an element of the director's language, with the help of which some information will be transmitted to the viewer" [9, p. 33].

Many researchers agree with this definition (Romanova, 2008; Snetkova, 2009; Bodrova, 2009; Lavrynenko, 2010, etc.), although it should be noted that some authors (Zaretska, 2010) believe that it covers a too wide range of manifestations, including advertising video, music clip, etc., which brings it closer to the definition of a media text.

Basic material presentation. Considering that the film cannot be unambiguously classified as exclusively linguistic or exclusively non-linguistic phenomena, it is necessary to emphasize the interpretation of semiotically heterogeneous communicative phenomena of a synthetic nature. In linguistics, they are understood as creolized, heterogeneous, polymodal, polycode.

Texts whose texture consists of two inhomogeneous parts (verbal and non-verbal) are called creolized. The term "heterogeneous texts" is synonymous with the term "creolized texts". Heterogeneous texts combine semiotically heterogeneous components (images and words). It is assumed that words can be graphic signs, or they can be sonorous. In the case of a combination of an image and a sound word, two channels (visual and

acoustic) are involved in the perception of a heterogeneous message. In this case, we are talking about poly-modal (multimodal) texts, because they not only contain heterogeneous symbolic components, but are also perceived due to the simultaneous operation of two or more perceptual (sensory) modalities. At the same time, "the peculiarities of complex texts, which include heterogeneous components, allow us to define as their key properties polycode as a combination in a single space of works of different semiotic nature and poly-modality as the use of different sensory modalities of an individual's perception" [10, p. 22-23].

Polycode texts, which are understood as texts of a complex semiotic nature, are close to this understanding of markedly heterogeneous communicative phenomena. They represent a combination of verbal text in oral or written form, images, as well as signs of a different nature [V. E. Chernyavska, I. S. Shevchenko and others]. Polycode texts differ in the number of interacting sign systems. Among the most complex, R. O. Jacobson called musicals, especially cinematographic ones, - "very complex syncretic formations that combine a number of audio and visual semiotic means" [13, p. 321].

Despite the fact that the interpretation of the film as a creolized text was criticized in some linguistic and cultural works, E. E. Anisimova's definition is logical and well-founded: a creolized text is "a special linguo-visual phenomenon, a text in which verbal and pictorial components form one visual, structural, a meaningful and functional whole, which ensures its comprehensive pragmatic impact on the addressee" [1, p. 73].

From the point of view of E. V. Kozlov, who focuses on considering, first of all, the non-verbal components of the creolized text, they perform technical, informative and aesthetic functions. The technical function means the organization of the visual perception of the text, the information function is in the transmission of the content of the text, the aesthetic function is in the actualization of the author's artistic intention [4, p. 71].

Summarizing the components of the film text highlighted in the literature, it can be stated that the film text consists of moving and static images, spoken and written speech, noises and music, which are organized in a special way and are in an inseparable unity. Moreover, there are two semiotic systems in the film text – lingual and non-linguistic – which operate with different kinds of signs.

According to the classification of Ch. Peirce, signs are divided into three groups according to the nature of the relationship between the signifier and the signified:

- signs-icons formed on the basis of the similarity of the signifier and the signified;
- signs-indexes created by the relation of contiguity of signifier and signified;
- signs-symbols generated by establishing a connection between the signifier and the signified according to a conditional agreement [8].

The linguistic system of the film text is served by signs-symbols, that is, words, when non-linguistic – by signs-indexes and signs-icons.

In turn, the linguistic system in the film text is represented by two components: written (titles and inscriptions that are part of the world of things in the film – a poster, the name of a street or city, entrance and exit, letter or note, etc.) and oral (the speech of the actors, off-screen text, song, etc.), which are expressed using symbolic signs – words of natural language.

The non-linguistic system of the film text includes iconic and indexical signs. It also has a sound component – natural noises (sounds of rain, wind, footsteps, voices of animals and birds), technical noises and music. In addition, the non-linguistic system includes a video series – iconic and / or indexical signs (people, animals, fantastic creatures, objects) that carry out a sequence (chain) of movements, which are also iconic and / or indexical signs (gesticulation, facial expressions, pantomime, manipulation of objects, various types of movement and other actions, for example, explosions, accidents and natural disasters, which are carried out with the help of special effects). All of the above is a vocabulary of cinematography, or a unit of film text.

Speaking about the categorical features of the text in films, it should be noted that the specificity of most of the general text categories of the film is determined by the two-level structure characteristic of cinema and the predominance of the audience level in the film. Some researchers suggest the following characteristic features of the film text as a text.

1. The film text is a discrete unit, since its structure allows for division.

2. The coherence inherent in the film text: the meaningful independence of the episode is relative, because it requires reliance on the entire film text. So, we can talk about the film text as "a single coherent whole".

3. The direction of the development of events in the film text can be both the one that moves forward (according to the course of events in the real world) and the one that "returns". There is also prospecting and retrospection in the narrow sense – predicting the future, looking ahead and remembering the past. These categories create a sense of the multidimensionality of the world of the film text.

4. In the centre of the film text, regardless of the specific topic of the story, as a rule, there is a specific person, which speaks of the anthropocentrism of the film text.

5. The film text also has a local and temporal relevance. The space in the film text is often not free from the presence of the character, inseparable from the time of the action, and time flows unevenly for the audience.

6. The film text is characterized by multi-channel "informativeness": on the one hand, the information flow is divided by the method of information perception (visual and auditory), on the other – by the type of perceived information (content-factual, content-conceptual, content-subtext).

7. In the film text, nothing exists by chance, by itself: each element is included in the general system (systemicity), which is created by the collective author as a result of multiple semiotic transformations and functions to fulfil a single goal.

8. The specificity of the integrity category in the film text is as follows:

- a) close integration of linguistic and non-linguistic components;
- b) the presence of clear time and space frameworks;
- c) the presence of signals indicating the beginning and end of the film.

9. The film text is a product of the collective author's subjective understanding of reality. Considering the differentiated multi-author nature of the film text, researchers speak of a complex type of modality. Cinematography is a reflection of the world seen through the eyes of a group of people.

10. The pragmatic orientation of the film text is an encouragement of the recipient to the appropriate reaction, which in this case involves some implicit action, that is, a change in the viewer's feelings and thoughts, which does not necessarily find verbal expression.

Conclusion. It can be stated that the film text has the main textual characteristics (such as divisibility, coherence, prospection and retrospection, anthropocentricity, local and temporal relevance, informativeness, systematicity, integrity, modality and pragmatic orientation). At the same time, the film text has a number of unique properties that distinguish it from other types of text.

Semiotically heterogeneous discursive formations of a synthetic nature are understood in linguistics as creolized, heterogeneous, polymodal, polycode. Film discourse is a complex multi-level semiotic phenomenon, woven from subsystems of signs that form a certain hierarchy. Signs of the first order are combined into more complex signs of the second order, which, in turn, form even more complex signs of the third order. The latter are not a sum of values, but qualitatively new values, which collectively endows film discourse with the property of non-additivity.

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